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BAMBOO SHOOTS - NUTRITIONAL BENEFITS

A. Dharmendran and D. Jeeva

INTRODUCTION

Common name is Bamboo Shoot; Biological names are *Bambusa vulgaris* and *Phyllostachys edulis* and in Hindi name is Baans. Names in other Indian languages are Moongil Kuruthu (Tamil), Mulankoombu (Malayalam), Veduru Chiguru (Telugu), Bansberankur (Bengali), Kalkipan (Marathi), Baunsagaja (Oriya) and Baans (Urdu & Punjabi).

Bamboo shoots, or bamboo sprouts, are young stems that are harvested before they turn two weeks old and reach a height of 30 cm. Crispy and crunchy, bamboo shoots are valued for their delightfully supple texture and rich aroma. Native to Asia, bamboo shoots form an essential ingredient in the kitchens of China, India, Nepal, Indonesia, Vietnam, Philippines, Japan and Uganda. The edible bamboo shoots are of two varieties - winter and spring. Spring shoots are larger and tougher compared to the winter shoots, though both are available in fresh and canned forms. Snacks, curries, stir-fries, soups, salads and fried rice are just a few of the delicacies that make use of bamboo

shoots. Besides, they contain a certain nutritive value.

HISTORY

Members of the grass family, bamboo shoots were indigenous to southern China. They are the young and new canes of the bamboo plant, which is extremely versatile. Since ancient times, the woody tree trunks of bamboo have been used to build entire houses, furniture, kitchenware and utensils. Bamboo has also laid the foundation for many bridges and musical instruments, apart from the shoots being widely used as food. Due to its diverse adjustability to a wide range of climates, cultivation of bamboo shoots spread across different continents, from the tropical jungles of Chile to the mountain slopes of the Himalayas. But, owing to the weather conditions, bamboo shoots could not be cultivated in Canada, Europe, Antarctica and Western Asia, although successful efforts have been made in Northern Italy, which has mild winters and hot, humid summers. Today, bamboo shoots are commercially cultivated in Eastern and South Eastern Asia on extensive levels. However, this paper emphasizes the nutritional and health benefits of bamboo shoots and their potential for utilization as a health food.

NUTRITIONAL BENEFITS OF BAMBOO SHOOTS

Did you also know that you can eat bamboo shoots? The young shoots that emerge from the ground are tender and full of nutritional value. Read on to discover following nutritional benefits of bamboo shoots.

Bamboo Shoots after Harvesting

Low Caloric Content: A 100 gram serving of bamboo shoots contains only 20 calories. Also, the carbohydrates found in bamboo shoots do not amount to more than 5.2 grams per 100 gram serving.

Low Sugar Content: The amount of sugar found in bamboo shoots is about 2.5 grams per 100 gram serving. This is less than the amount of sugar found in many fruits and vegetables.

Negligible Amount of Fat: A serving of 100 grams of bamboo shoots contains less than 0.3 grams of fat. This fat consists of both saturated and unsaturated fats. Unsaturated fats are needed by the body and they can control the spread of bad Low Density Lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol throughout the body.

Source of Protein: A 100 gram serving of bamboo shoots would have about 2 to 2.6 grams of protein. The proteins found in bamboo consist of seventeen essential amino acids and two semi-essential amino acids.

Vitamins and Minerals: Bamboo shoots contain vitamins such as vitamin A, vitamin B6, vitamin E, thiamin, riboflavin, niacin, folate and pantothenic acid. Minerals found in bamboo shoots include calcium, magnesium, phosphorous, potassium, sodium, zinc, copper, manganese, selenium and iron.

Dietary Fiber: The amounts of dietary fiber contained in bamboo shoots make up 2.2 grams out of a 100 gram serving.

Appetizing effects: Bamboo shoots contain high cellulosic material which stimulates the appetite. The taste and texture of the bamboo shoots also make them a good appetizer. Read on further to know more about the nutritional value of bamboo shoots from the table given below.

Nutritional Value of Raw Bamboo Shoot

Nutrition value per 100 g. (Source: USDA National Nutrient data base)		
Principle	Nutrient Value	Percentage
Energy	27 Kcal	1.4%
Carbohydrates	5.2 g	4%
Protein	2.60 g	5%
Total Fat	0.3 g	1%
Cholesterol	0 mg	0%
Dietary Fiber	2.2 g	6%
Vitamins		
Folates	7 µg	2%
Niacin	0.600 mg	4%
Pantothenic acid	0.161 mg	3%
Pyridoxine	0.240 mg	18%
Riboflavin	0.070 mg	5%
Thiamin	0.150 mg	12%
Vitamin C	4 mg	7%
Vitamin A	20 IU	<1%
Vitamin E	1 mg	7%
Vitamin K	0 µg	0%
Electrolytes		
Sodium	4 mg	<1%
Potassium	533 mg	11%
Minerals		
Calcium	13 mg	1.5%
Copper	0.190 mg	21%
Iron	0.50 mg	6%
Magnesium	3 mg	<1%
Manganese	0.262 mg	11%
Phosphorus	59 mg	8%
Selenium	0.8 µg	1.5%
Zinc	1.10 mg	10%
Phyto-nutrients		
Carotene-β	12 µg	
Carotene-?	0 µg	
Lutein-zeaxanthin	0 µg	

Units:mg = milligrams, µg = micrograms
IU = International units.

HEALTH BENEFITS OF BAMBOO SHOOTS

Bamboo shoots are an exotic food that is consumed in many countries in Asia and now it is slowly growing in demand from western countries. Bamboo shoots are known for their various health benefits, including those explained in greater detail below.

Weight Loss: Bamboo shoots are weight loss

Bamboo Shoots with outside layers

friendly. When we look at the amount of calories, carbohydrates and sugars contained in bamboo shoots, it is shocking to find that their presence is almost negligible. This makes it an ideal food for people who want to lose weight, but also who want their stomachs to be full.

Healthy Skin and Hair: Silica is an important compound that plays a vital role in maintaining your skin and hair healthy. Bamboo extract is the rich sources of silica and hence its daily use is helpful in improving the condition of your skin and hair. Silica improves skin health by promoting better absorption of mineral like calcium, magnesium and potassium by your body. It has antioxidant properties that help in reducing wrinkles, fine lines and signs of aging.

Heart Health: According to research studies, phytosterols and phytonutrients found in bamboo shoots are ideal for dissolving harmful LDL cholesterol in the body. This eases cholesterol out of arteries for the smooth supply and movement of blood throughout the body.

Controls Cholesterol: Consumption of bamboo shoots is also helpful in decreasing LDL levels of cholesterol, with stable glucose levels. This is due to the fact that bamboo shoots contain negligible amounts of fat and very low calories. Research conducted by Park

and Jhon at Washington State University showed that the consumption of bamboo shoots had favorable effects on cholesterol, lipids and bowel function.

Anti - Cancer Properties: Research studies conducted on bamboo shoots have indicated that leaves of bamboo shoots consist of phytosterols such as flavone, amylase and chlorophyll. Out of these, chlorophyll showed properties of controlling mutations and cancer.

Immune System: The vitamins and minerals in bamboo shoots are ideal for improving the body's immune system. The vitamins, minerals, and antioxidants present in bamboo shoots are essential for strengthening the body from the inside out.

High Supply of Dietary Fiber: The amount of dietary fiber in bamboo shoots is high. Consuming sufficient amounts of dietary fiber is essential for easy digestion and healthy bowel movements. Including bamboo shoots in your meals can be a very good idea for losing weight as well. With lack of any physical activity during the night time, taking food with less calories and high fiber helps lose weight easily, even while you sleep!

Anti-Inflammatory Properties: According to research conducted by Muniappan and Sundararaj, bamboo shoots possess anti-inflammatory and analgesic (pain-killing)

Cooked Bamboo shoots

Bamboo Shoots with soaking water

properties. It helps in the healing of ulcers as well. Juice from bamboo shoots can also be used as a medicine for external wounds and ulcers.

Bone Health: Bamboo shoot contains minerals like calcium, potassium and magnesium that are associated with the growth and development of healthy bones. The silica in bamboo is helpful in increasing bone mass and preventing conditions like osteoporosis.

Respiratory Disorders: Bamboo shoots have been known to be effective against respiratory disorders. A decoction of the shoots can be prepared by boiling the shoots twice. The first boil should be for 5 minutes followed by a second boil for about 10 minutes. The decoction can be taken along with honey for the best effect.

Possible Cure for Poisoning: In Ayurvedic medicine, the ancient Indian science of medicine and lifestyle, it is believed that bamboo extracts contain anti-venomous properties. They are useful in cases of both snake and scorpion bites.

Uterotonic Properties: Traditional Chinese medicine believes that bamboo shoots can cause uterine contractions. It is used as a medicinal supplement during the last month of pregnancy when the delivery date is still

pending. According to the research paper submitted by Gruber and O'Brien at the University of Vienna, bamboo is one of the many plants which have been listed among uterotonic plants.

Stomach Disorders: Bamboo shoots are useful in treating stomach disorders. Apart from bamboo shoots, bamboo leaves are also suggested as a remedy for intestinal worms and stomach disorders as well.

Wound Cleaning: Bamboo shoots are also used for cleaning wounds and sores.

Lowers Blood Pressure: Bamboo shoots contain high amounts of potassium. Potassium is highly beneficial as an electrolyte and is also very good for lowering and maintaining blood pressure. With all of these benefits from bamboo shoots, they are highly recommended for a healthy lifestyle.

Removing Intestinal Worms: Drinking the juice of bamboo shoot can help in killing and eliminating intestinal worms.

STORAGE OF BAMBOO SHOOTS

Bamboo shoots can be obtained in either the fresh or canned form. Fresh shoots that are stored in the refrigerator will keep up to two weeks. After 2 weeks they will start developing a bitter taste. The bitterness also develops if the bamboo shoots is exposed to sunlight and so make sure to keep them in a cool, dark place. The canned form of bamboo shoot is easier to get when compared to the fresh forms. After opening the can, rinse the shoots in hot water before using them. Unused bamboo shoots can be kept in an air tight container filled with water and stored in the refrigerator. Make sure to change the water daily.

PREPARATION OF BAMBOO SHOOTS

Raw bamboo shoots are bitter in taste and can difficult to digest as it contains a cyanogenic

glycoside known as taxiphyllin, which produces cyanide inside the stomach. However, cooking the shoots properly will help in getting rid of the toxicity. So before eating, it is important to clean and cook the bamboo shoots to remove the bitter taste. Trim off the roots and remove any leaves or hard flesh of the shoots before you cook them. Cook the shoots in boiling water for about 20 to 25 minutes (some people suggest boiling for an hour). Leave the pan uncovered so that the substances that gives bitterness to the shoots escapes in to the air. If the bitterness still exists, cook the shoots for some more time. The bamboo shoot can then be sliced according to your choice and used in cooking. Another way to make them edible is to soak the shoots in water for about three days. Keep changing the water every day.

SERVING METHODS OF BAMBOO SHOOTS

Bamboo shoot is a popular ingredient in Chinese, Thailand, Indonesian and Vietnamese cooking. One way to enjoy bamboo shoot is to cut it into thin slices and cook it along with spices, vegetables and coconut milk. You can cut them julienne style (thin strips) and add them to stir fries, soups, salads, noodles and other dishes. Pickling the bamboo shoots in vinegar, salt and sugar is another way to enjoy its delicious taste. Add a little bit of butter, salt or soy sauce and pepper to bamboo shoots and serve them as a tasty side dish.

CONCLUSION

Bamboo is intricately associated with humans from times immemorial. Popularly known for their industrial uses, a lesser known fact of

bamboos is the usage of its young shoots as a food that can be consumed fresh, fermented, or canned. The juvenile shoots are not only delicious but are rich in nutrient components, mainly proteins, carbohydrates, minerals, and fiber and are low in fat and sugars. In addition, they contain phytosterols and a high amount of fiber that can be labeled as nutraceuticals or natural medicines that are attracting the attention of health advocates and scientists alike. The shoots are free from residual toxicity and grow without the application of fertilizers. Modern research has revealed that bamboo shoots have a number of health benefits such as improving appetite and digestion, weight loss, and curing cardiovascular diseases and cancer. The shoots are reported to have anti cancer, antibacterial, and antiviral activity. Shoots have antioxidant capacity due to the presence of phenolic compounds. The increasing trends of health consciousness among consumers have stimulated the field of functional foods and bamboo shoots can be one of them. Bamboo fiber is now a common ingredient in breakfast cereals, fruit juices, bakery and meat products, sauces, shredded cheeses, cookies, pastas, snacks, frozen desserts, and many other food products.

So if you wish to add some variety to your daily diet, why not try a new and creative recipe with bamboo shoot? Not only is this a low calorie and healthy option, it is easily available and extremely effortless to prepare.

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